

**BM-5102 | ORGANISATIONAL BEHAVIOUR
SEMESTER 1 2020/2021
REFLECTIVE REPORT**

20M1304

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Table of Contents:

1. OVERVIEW.....	3
2. THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL KNOWLEDGE.....	4
3. INDIVIDUAL OPINIONS AND CONTRIBUTIONS ON THE GROUP ASSIGNMENT.....	5
4. OPINIONS OF THE TEAM MEMBERS ON THE GROUP ASSIGNMENT	5
5. OUTCOMES OF THE GROUP ASSIGNMENT	6
6. INDIVIDUAL STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES.....	6
7. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CHANGES.....	7
8. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE REFLECTIVE REPORT	7
9. REFERENCES	8

1. OVERVIEW

The Master of Management (MM) programme in Universiti Brunei Darussalam (UBD) is a full-time 18 months programme commencing August of each academic year with the aim to develop knowledge and intellectual skills of graduates. A few months before completing my Bachelor Degree in History and International Studies, I was hesitating at first whether to pursue my Master's Degree or not. In choosing the right Master's programme is also becoming a huge issue because changing from History to Business programmes takes a lot of courage and additional effort to study. For the record, I was once a Business Management student from Politeknik Brunei back in 2013 to 2015. Thus, I gather my leftover courage in choosing Master of Management despite contemplating whether to continue with History or Business programmes. I was further convinced by one of my history lecturers and supervisors to straight away pursuing for a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in History. Nonetheless, it does not stop me from choosing MM as my Master's Degree programme.

Organisational Behaviour is one of the core modules for students taking MM in UBD. Since I have taken this module during my Advanced Diploma, I was trying to appeal to be exempted from taking this module as previously I got an A for this module. Nonetheless, there is no action taken by UBD nor the exam section. Thus, I have no choice but to retake this module for the second time as this is the core module in completing my Master's programme. Upon having this module in the first week, I figured out that the outlines are similar to my Advanced Diploma programme, hence, it is easier for me to cope with the online learning. However, in the second week of the module, I found that the lecturer is trying to teach us more towards practical knowledge rather than theoretical knowledge. This can be seen when she actually asked us to write a paper *Motivations Behind Pursuing Your MM*. Rather than teaching us in a traditional method of teaching, she taught us how to be independent on doing some research notes and references for a better understanding of her module. Based on the articles and guidelines that she provided to us, we were able to complete our paper on *Motivations Behind Pursuing Your MM* and have a clear understanding on the motivation topic rather than learning it from the book.

A few months after taking this module, I can easily relate my experience as a MM's programme student as I finally figure out a new perspective of life. For instance, having a good circle of friends encourage us to perform harder in completing the study. Moreover, with a good circle of friends lead to a good teamwork as we are free to choose our team members for any group assignments. Working together in the same group with familiar faces motivate ourselves to contribute and perform well, hence, success can be guaranteed since mutualities are crucial in every aspect, especially in working together as a group. Thus, I learned that good team members are part of my intrinsic motivation because I can interact and work together with friends that I like and trust. Simply to say that I enjoy a great deal of satisfaction of completing both my individual and group assignments as I receive endless support from my friends.

2. THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL KNOWLEDGE

Ramnani (2017) mentions that theoretical knowledge refers to when someone is learning without adapting the practical approach where it gives a deeper understanding of a concept and the reason behind it. In contrast, practical knowledge teaches someone about the real life experience and often leads to a deeper understanding through personal experience. Hence, the application of practical knowledge along with theory gives a clear explanation about the facts.

The most obvious thing that I discovered was the online learning for this first semester of Master of Management. The online learning was practiced in the university ever since the outbreak of the COVID-19 in Brunei Darussalam starting in early March 2020. I learned that most of us felt difficult to cope with online learning as most of us are not from the Business programme back when we did our Bachelor Degree. As mentioned by Seifert and Sutton (2018), they state that there are six major theories of motives for learning such as motives as behaviour change, motives as goals, motives as interests, motives as attributions about success, motives as beliefs about self-efficacy and motives as self-determination. Thus, I believe that my motives of learning depend on the goal that I have set in order to support my academic achievement. Therefore, I find it interesting in learning Organisational Behaviour for this semester because I believe that this module will be useful in later courses, hence, it can be considered as a mastery goal because I want to learn or master the module for a good reference in the future courses. Seifert and Sutton (2018) state that mastery goal is part of intrinsic motivation where it tends to be linked with enjoyment of learning the module and students with this goal tend to enroll in further courses in the same subject.

In addition, Maslow's hierarchy of needs that we have learned from this module is also crucial in reflecting our life in the university. As mentioned previously, the lecturer is asking us to write a paper on what motivates us to pursue our study in MM at the beginning of the study. Thus, I figured out that I should relate to what we have learned so far in the class by linking back the theories being taught in class. I identified Maslow's hierarchy of needs as my motivational theory in completing my study in MM. Maslow's hierarchy of needs includes the lower-order needs and higher-order needs. The lower-order needs comprises of physiological, safety and social concerns while the higher-order needs include esteem and self-actualization concerns (Schermerhorn, 2013).

What satisfies higher-order needs?	
Self-actualization needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Challenging tasks, as most of the assignments are doing research papers.• Participation in decision making, as we are free to choose our own topic for the research papers.

Esteem needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Praise and recognition from lecturers. • Feel the responsibility of completing the study.
What satisfies lower-order needs?	
Social needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good teamwork for the group assignment. • Positive interaction with new friends. • Pleasant and supportive lecturers.
Safety needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safe and conducive learning environment.
Physiological needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inflexible online learning for some of the modules.

Figure 1: Maslow’s theory of completing my study in Master of Management

3. INDIVIDUAL OPINIONS AND CONTRIBUTIONS ON THE GROUP ASSIGNMENT

My contributions in the group comprise of choosing the right case study for the group as well as structuring the table of contents for the report. This is because the selected case study is a current issue that is happening in Brunei Darussalam at the moment, hence, choosing the right case study for the group based on first come first serve may be beneficial for the group. Furthermore, I am also contributing more on the literature review part, since other members are compiling the findings for further actions to be taken. Nonetheless, all of the team members have a good team work on doing the report, such as creating the survey questions together in a virtual meeting, creating Google Forms to be distributed to participants, analyzing the data and findings.

4. OPINIONS OF THE TEAM MEMBERS ON THE GROUP ASSIGNMENT

For the group assignment, a total of four members namely Khairunissa, Liyana, Muqri and myself are grouped together to complete the assignment. Begin as a total stranger for MM programme, we were able to work together in sync without any problems as each of us have been assigned to different roles in the group. As mentioned by Nissa, she states that I am quick in finishing the task that has been assigned. She also adds that I am good at proofreading and finalizing the group report. Meanwhile, Liyana mentions the similar feature of myself as being quick in finishing the assigned task and further argues that I am good at structuring the table of contents for the report. On the other hand, Muqri states that I am relatively quick in obtaining

relevant data that can be beneficial to our report as well as responsible in making sure that the group is on the right track. As everyone had their own opinions and ideas, many different perspectives could be produced. Furthermore, I figured out that the energy of the group participation made me feel more motivated on contributing my ideas and energy to complete the group report.

5. OUTCOMES OF THE GROUP ASSIGNMENT

I believe that the outcome of this group assignment is a success. Considering that all of us are relatively new to each other, we were able to work together as one unit without having arguments and misunderstanding. Everyone is being aware of their own roles in the group which turn out that the group report can be completed earlier than the submission date. Furthermore, the group also has no issue on the ethics application as well as findings as every each of us learned that good teamwork is the key to success in writing a research report when time and resources are limited. The group report, with the research focusing on the behaviour and attitude of university students in Brunei Darussalam towards online learning gave an insight on how COVID-19 has affected the learning of students in the university.

The results of this research also highlighted the comparative result between local and international university students, in which it gives a similar result of students' perceptions that it is a good alternative to learn something new like online learning as it saves their time. Hence, the result of this research can be useful for researchers who are trying to do a comparative study between local and international students, particularly in the area of ethical attitudes and behaviours specifically under the condition of the global COVID-19 pandemic. Other than that, further research can be conducted by researchers who are interested in this area of research as the study is only limited to four public universities in Brunei Darussalam by using surveys as the main method. Thus, the data and the result can be considered as insufficient. Nonetheless, this study met the objectives as it clearly highlighted the crucial findings of ethical behaviours and attitudes of university students who are using online platforms as their online learning.

6. INDIVIDUAL STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES

Upon experiencing this module with both individual and group assignments, I figured out my strengths and weaknesses in learning this module. First, I have learned that we need to be more active and quick in gathering data and resources as it helps us to quickly decide on what research topic can be chosen based on articles that we have read before. I figured out that my strength is to be able to grasp the topic that I have interest upon completing the third week of learning this module. I have more interest in learning in the area of motivation theories and practices which leads me to choose a research paper based on this topic. Consequently, I came up with a research topic as *Motivation Theories and Practices: A Case Study of Score-A-Smart Tuition School from Teachers' Perspectives*. I was able to gather and complete the data through semi-structured interviews and I figured out that acquiring their trusts in interviews need some skills as a researcher. Thus, I believed that my strength includes communication skills in acquiring data from semi-structured interviews as this is very useful for every researcher.

However, my weakness includes being a bossy for the group. As I believe that assignments should be done as early as possible, hence, I keep on putting some pressures to my team members in a way that I am dividing and delivering the tasks accordingly without asking their opinion first. Furthermore, I always try to conduct a physical meeting with the group by pushing them that the deadline is getting near. I learned that this autocratic leadership style is best fit for me and might be my weakness for the group. Nonetheless, the outcome is positive as my team members mentioned that it is in a way for them to ensure that the group is on the right track and able to finish on time. Consequently, we were able to complete the group assignment two weeks before the submission date.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CHANGES

I believe that a good team work is a key for the success of pursuing MM as it is part of the intrinsic motivation. This is because when we work together, we learned many different perspectives and strengths of each of the team members, hence, can improve what we are lacking in certain ways. Therefore, in working as a group, I learned that autocratic leadership style may be good or bad depending on the situations and the person. Depending on the situation, it may be good for the group who needs guidance on how to start and structure an assignment. However, it may be bad for the group who have different opinions on how to begin with the assignment. As for the person, autocratic leadership style may be good for the people who likes to be led, but may be bad for the people who tend to like the participative leadership style. Thus, I value the friendship and relationship of the group members as I have learned that not everyone favours this type of autocratic leadership style. Therefore, in the future, I might want to change the leadership style of leading the members in a more participative way so that everyone can voice out their opinions.

8. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE REFLECTIVE REPORT

Reflective report can be useful to analyze own experiences, practices, skills or responses so that students can learn, reflect and improve their academic practices. In many cases, this report allows students to demonstrate and write critically their own skills or practices that they have learned, but at the same time analyzing it in order to improve and emphasize on how to apply what they have learned in different settings (University of Birmingham, 2020). Therefore, upon completing this core module, my experience involving being independent in learning the module with limited source of time to complete the assignments can be used in the future as I learned on not to depend heavily on the lecture notes from the lecturer as million of sources can easily be accessed by us in different authoritative websites. The skills of learning on how to peer review students is also becoming handy and useful as we learned about what are the other strengths and weaknesses of others so that we can read, share, comment and improve each other writing in a way that helping each other out for a good cause. Moreover, one of the most key important methods to complete the assignment is that by updating the report every week to the lecturer as writing it every week becomes a habit for us, hence, teaching us to keep on writing to chase the deadline. Thus, we learned that time never waits for us, but we are the one who needs to be more energetic and eager to chase the time.

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